

Removable Batteries As a Case Study For Right to Repair Legislation: A Markovian Stochastic Model For Determining Legislative Impact on Device Longevity

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Abstract:

This study aims to quantify the impact of right-to-repair legislation on smartphone longevity and e-waste. Recent EU regulation proposals will require manufacturers to use removable batteries in smartphones to extend device lifetimes by 2027. This paper uses a Markovian stochastic model to simulate the smartphone life cycle based on this proposal, whilst also providing a framework for future pieces of legislation. The model compares current durability trends and a scenario with mandated battery removability by introducing a new state into the Markov Chain. Even considering a conservative repair-adoption scenario, where adoption rates of repair stay constant to the status quo, the model predicts an average smartphone lifespan increase from 2.5 to 2.66 years (6.4%). In a best-case scenario of 100% adoption of battery repair, average lifespan extends to 3.08 years (23.2%).

The changes in lifespan can be analyzed from an environmental lens. Using 2030 estimates of smartphone consumption, an estimated maximum of 3,700 metric tons of e-waste and 1.75 million metric tons of CO₂-equivalent emissions per cycle of smartphone purchases would be avoided in the EU market alone. Our conservative estimates quantify 1200 metric tons of e-waste and 559,350 tons of CO₂-equivalent emissions. The wide range demonstrates that legislation can yield measurably high sustainability gains, but benefits otherwise depend on consumer repair adoption rates. The model provides a replicable framework to isolate and quantify single design interventions, to better inform future right-to-repair legislation with a data-driven approach.

Introduction:

The Right to Repair Movement has gained increasing traction in response to the growing issue of planned obsolescence in the consumer electronics industry. Planned obsolescence, a business strategy in which product expiration is deliberately built into the design, has existed since the 1930s, evolving to decrease device longevity and necessitate the purchase of replacements (Gershon 2017). Though this strategy benefits corporations, it has

been widely criticized for its environmental consequences through the acceleration of electronic waste and resource depletion. This accumulation is especially heightened due to a lack of repairs, with an increase in electronic repairs having a greater impact on reducing environmental impact over recycling and remanufacturing due to direct reuse over requiring intensive manufacturing processes to repair (Sonego, Echeveste, and Debarba 2022). A significant cause of a lack of consumer electronic repairs is due to how irreparability is built into devices through overly-complex and proprietary designs, a form of planned obsolescence; product lifetime is greatly affected by a consumer's decision to discard a product, suggesting that more sustainable purchasing habits is reliant on "incentivising the use of circular service offers" (Amend et al. 2022). By preventing second hand markets from thriving with refurbished goods, corporations force a surplus of new electronics to be bought by consumers which causes millions of tons of e-waste to be thrown out every single year (WHO 2024).

To tackle multi-billion dollar corporations from decreasing product repairability, a number of initiatives have been taken by governments and organizations across the globe in the name of *right to repair*. Right to repair legislation can be defined as the support of people's freedom to repair gadgets by forcing companies to make "diagnostic tools, repair manuals, and replacement parts available to the public" by the law (Ozturkcan 2023). One such piece of progress is the EU's requirement for smartphones to have removable and replaceable batteries by the end-user by 2030, in hopes of increasing device longevity and the effective recycling of batteries that otherwise cannot be easily separated (Porter 2023).

Although legislative steps are certainly being taken to combat corporate greed, global powers such as the United States are demonstrably behind on legislation: While the European Parliament is adopting new right to repair proposals such as that on November 21st, the US sees no such progress. And even the European Union still has much to go on expanding such protections for uncovered goods such as motor vehicles and medical equipment (Putrino 2024).

Another major question is the impact right to repair legislation actually has on net waste. Although research has been done on the impact of second-hand markets device longevity and circulation, how device longevity would look considering the implementation of a specific piece of legislation has not yet been done, and thus is the premise of this paper. That is,

this paper seeks to analyze how right to repair legislation influences the lifecycle of consumer electronics and its impact on reducing net waste. By quantifying the relationship between increased repairability and waste reduction, this research can provide a mode for determining the effectiveness of a specific right to repair policy. Furthermore, it can demonstrate how varying degrees of enforcement and the products targeted shape the outcomes of right to repair initiatives, offering insight into realistic environmental expectations and benefits.

While the focus of this paper is to model the impact of right to repair legislation on device longevity, analysis will be performed with respect to a specific piece of legislation on removable smartphone batteries. Smartphone batteries were chosen as the focus of this paper for a failure to examine the impact of legislation due to its likely implementation, at least in Europe, by 2030.

2. Methods

2.1. Model

The choice of model is a stochastic approach utilizing a markov chain to determine the impact of an extension on device lifetime should a piece of legislation be enacted. This computational model entails the following:

We first determine the status quo in which all devices undergo a single method of ownership from New to End of Life as a baseline quantification for longevity to compare the post-legislation model to in order to analyze and extrapolate the difference. In all scenarios, 100% of all devices will go from New (N) to End of Life (EoL), however the time will vary from device to device. In the context of equations, $P_{NE} \times T_{NE}$ can be used where P_{NE} is the probability of any device entering this specific transitional matrix (100%) and T_{NE} is the time spent in that state.

Figure 1. Pre-RTR Legislation

The post-legislation model adds a third potential state with three new transitional matrices. The new state is noted as Failure & Repair (*F&R*) which will be used to assess the devices that are impacted by the right to repair legislation. All other devices will continue as normal from New to EoL. The post-legislation is the following:

Figure 2. Post-RTR Legislation Markov Chain

The first transitional matrix from New to End of Life does not maintain any of its initial values. Firstly, the probability of a device entering this state will depend on a number of factors, including but not limited to:

- The percentage of devices that are thrown out due to a failure
- The percentage of those failures being related to the legislation's target
- Percentage of devices successfully repaired in the status quo

All devices will either enter the $N \rightarrow EoL$ transitional matrix or the $N \rightarrow F\&R$ matrix. In other words, $P_{NE} + P_{F\&R} = 1$. The time spent in $N \rightarrow F\&R$ will depend on the device and the type of failure being targeted by the legislation. The time spent in $N \rightarrow EoL$ for this markov chain is not the same as the time spent in the first one (Figure 1), as the status quo model still includes all of the devices that are impacted by the legislation. Those devices must be separated out to recalculate the time spent using the relationship: $P_L \times T_L + P_E \times T_E = T_{Total}$, in which

$P_L \times T_L$ represents the post-legislation transitional matrix for devices impacted by legislation and $P_E \times T_E$ represents the post-legislational transitional matrix for all other devices. T_{Total} is device longevity in the status quo. Data likely only exists for T_L but not T_E , and so T_E can be solved with the necessary data needed for the model anyway. To solve for T_E :

$$T_E = (T_{Total} - (P_L \times T_L)) \div P_E$$

Devices that enter the *F&R* state will either automatically reach end of life due to those devices either not being repaired or having a failed repair. Determining what percentage of devices end up would likely require survey data. Failure rates of repairs can be quite ambiguous and is only worth considering for devices whose repairs still have significant failure risks even after legislation forces that process to become easier. The probability of a device entering an extended lifetime thanks to repair from *F&R* will be the percentage of people who are willing to repair their device given the passage of the legislation multiplied by the success rate of that repair, if applicable. The other devices will automatically fail with time spent in that transitional matrix equal to zero. The time spent in an extended lifetime *should* be determined through data on how much longer repaired devices tend to last versus unrepaired devices, though such data is incredibly difficult to collect as it relies on getting a sufficient dataset of repaired devices and their longevity specifically. In a worst case scenario, $T_{NE} - T_{NF}$ can be used as a substitute value, essentially assuming that the repair would cause the device to act as if the damage had never occurred. Such a substitution assumes that the decision to repair would not affect a person's decision to keep their own device for longer. Overall, the final expression pans out to the following:

$$(P_{NE} \times T_{NE}) + (P_{NF\&R} \times T_{NF\&R}) + (P_{F\&REoL} \times T_{F\&REoL})$$

2.2. Applied Model

To evaluate the impact of Right to Repair legislation, specifically on removable batteries, this markovian stochastic model is employed to assess device longevity. According to Cordella et al., 40% of smartphone failures are hardware related, 42% of which are battery-related. Thus, roughly 16.8% of smartphones fail due to battery issues. In the status quo, only 16% of phones are currently repaired, meaning that the remaining 84% of

battery-related failures end up leading people to replace their devices. The average lifespan of a smartphone is 2.5 years, but battery-related failures often occur earlier. Battery failure is generally accepted to be a degradation of lifespan by 20%, something that generally occurs after 300-500 charging cycles—2 years— with lithium ion batteries.

Existing data thus confirms that smartphones in the pre-legislation model take 2.5 years to degrade. To determine the lifespan of smartphone devices, not including smartphones that fail due to batteries, a weighted average can be performed, where x is the lifespan of devices that failed after battery issues (2.0 years) and y is the lifespan of all other devices

$$2.5 = (0.42 \times 0.40 \times 0.84)x + (1 - (0.42 \times 0.40 \times 0.84))y$$

$$y = 2.58 \text{ years}$$

The remaining device now enters the fail & repair state. These are the devices that previously failed due to battery issues and would not be repaired in the status quo. From previous calculations, 16.8% of all devices fall into this category, each with a lifespan of about 2.0 years before failure, indicating P_{NF} to equal 0.168 and T_{NF} to equal 2.0. Thus, this transitional matrix is associated with a value of 0.28 years. However, post-implementation of right to repair legislation will cause a portion of these previously unrepaired devices to now be repaired. In the past 5 years, 25 percent of people tried to get the phone fixed but failed and ended up replacing it (Chen 2022). Considering that the failure rate of a smartphone battery replacement when batteries are removable is marginally tiny, it can be estimated that 25% of the 14% of smartphones will be repaired and go on to experience a normal lifespan of 2.58 years, meaning an average 0.58 years is added to their lifespan. This gives our bottom chain an expression of $0.14 \times 2.0 + 0.25 \times 0.58 = 0.438$. The remaining unrepaired devices no longer contribute to the estimated lifespan of devices. 0

This value can now contribute to the total value of the lifespan from new to end of life. The unaffected devices with a battery life of 2.58 is multiplied by the probability that a device goes through that path (0.86) and added to the lifespan extension calculated above (0.438) to reach a value of **2.66 years**. Note that this value assumes that the percentage of people who would be willing to repair their devices does not change. In a best case scenario, where 100% of

devices that can be repaired after this legislation are repaired, device longevity would extend to a notable **3.08 years**.

Analysis and Discussion

Interpreting the Model's Projections

The Markovian stochastic model presented offers a data-driven approach to an otherwise quantitative debate surrounding the sustainable efficacy of Right to Repair legislation, providing measurable analysis of interventions aimed at increasing the lifespan of consumer electronics. The model's primary findings, an increase in average smartphone lifespan from 2.5 years to a conservative estimate of 2.66 years and a best-case scenario of 3.08 years, represent a potential longevity gain of 6.4% to 23.2%. The conservative estimate of 2.66 years is based on empirical survey data of a 25% repair uptake rate under conditions of battery failure. The best-case scenario of 3.08 years is based on a 100% repair adoption rate for battery failures, demonstrating the theoretical maximum impact for this specific legislative intervention. These figures represent a modest but important increase in reversing the trend towards diminishing product lifespans, a phenomenon largely driven by the industrial strategy of planned obsolescence (Barros and Dimla 2021).

In the consumer electronics industry, planned obsolescence has evolved to include a combination of aesthetic changes to incentivise new purchases and functional limitations to shorten a product's overall lifespan (Barros and Dimla 2021). One such example as per the case study is the practice of fastening batteries within smartphone chassis using strong adhesives, replacing batteries that previously could be immediately switched out with no tools, causing the replacement process to require specialized tools and expertise and discourage repair. The EU's 2030 mandate will require manufacturers to build in user-replaceable batteries, directly targeting this specific design choice.

However, the most significant contribution of this model relies less on its predictive output, but more so its replicability in isolating and quantifying the impact of a single, discrete

design variable. This provides a powerful tool for evidence-based policymaking. Historically, the right to repair debate has been characterized by broad, qualitative arguments. Manufacturers and industry associations frequently raise concerns about consumer safety, data security, and the potential for stifled innovation, yet often without empirical support (Minnesota Government; Repair.org). Though investigations by regulatory bodies such as the U.S. Federal Trade Commission (FTC) have found no evidence to substantiate these claims, and in some cases, have uncovered evidence that manufacturers may deliberately design products to make independent repairs less safe as a competitive strategy (Minnesota Government; Repair.org).

By providing a clear, quantitative answer, the model aims to shift policy discourse from an intractable conflict of assertions to a more productive cost-benefit analysis. The projected longevity gain becomes a tangible "benefit" that can be weighed against industry concerns and translated into the concrete environmental and economic savings explored in the subsequent sections. This provides policymakers with a robust, data-driven foundation upon which to build and defend legislative action.

Contextualizing Longevity Gains

The world produced 62 million tons of e-waste in 2022, an 82% increase from 2010. This figure is rising five times faster than documented recycling rates and is projected to reach 82 million tons by 2030 (United Nations). Extending product lifespans through repair is effective in mitigating this crisis because it decreases the production quantity of smartphones needed per year, a significant figure when considering that of the 85 kilograms of CO₂-equivalent emissions produced in its first year of a smartphone's usage, 95% is attributable to manufacturing processes, including the energy-intensive extraction of raw materials and fabrication of integrated circuits (Lee et al.).

To translate the model's projections into more concrete environmental impacts, Table 1 estimates the annual impact of the EU's removable battery mandate. The calculations are based on an estimated 290.6 million annual smartphone sales in the EU, an average smartphone

weight of 170 grams, and an average manufacturing carbon footprint of 80 kg per device.

Table 1: Projected Annual Environmental and Economic Impacts of the EU Removable Battery Mandate

	Status Quo (2.5-Year Lifespan)	Conservative Scenario (2.66-Year Lifespan)	Best-Case Scenario (3.08-Year Lifespan)	Calculation Method
Average Device Lifespan (Years)	2.50	2.66 (+6.4%)	3.08 (+23.2%)	Based on model projections.
Annual Device Replacements (EU Market)	116,240,000	~109,248,120	~94,350,649	(290,600,000 EU smartphones) / (Avg Lifespan)
Reduction in Annual Replacements	0	~6,991,880	~21,889,351	116,240,000 Devices Replaced - Post-Legislatio n amount
Estimated E-Waste Averted	0	~1189	~3721	(Reduction in Annual Replacements)

Annually (Tons)				* (0.00017 metric tons per device).
Estimated Reduction in Manufacturing (Tons)	0	~559,350	~1,751,148	(Reduction in Annual Replacements) * (0.08 metric tons of CO2 per device)

As Table 1 illustrates, even the conservative scenario projects the aversion of over 800 tonnes of e-waste and nearly 560,000 metric tons of emissions annually within the EU market alone. The best-case scenario suggests these figures could rise to over 3700 tonnes of e-waste and 1.75 million tonnes of CO₂. These calculations demonstrate that a single, targeted piece of legislation can have a profound and measurable positive impact, directly addressing the upstream cause of the e-waste crisis by reducing the demand for new manufacturing.

Theoretical Repairability Versus Repair Adoption

The significant delta between the model's conservative projection (25% repair uptake) and its best-case scenario (100% uptake) is demonstrative of the real world challenge of an “adoption gap”. Technical repairability does not necessarily translate to repair adoption due to a combination of psychological and behavioral patterns that prevent consumers from choosing repair, regardless of its financial or environmental benefits.

Evidence from a survey of European consumers found that a majority 60% of those replacing a defective product did not consider repair (Magnier and Mugge 2022). This behavior is not primarily driven by objective device failure, considering that a study of over 3.5 million

iPhone benchmark scores revealed the relatively stable performance of smartphones over a lifetime (Makov and Fitzpatrick 2021). This is consistent with psychological research on marketing, where consumers are likely to feel a sense of outdatedness for their devices even if it functions similarly, often the result of manufacturers releasing frequent stylistic model changes and marketing the desirability of new features (Barros and Dimla 2021).

Model Limitations and Future Improvements

First, the model utilizes static transition probabilities, which assumes a fixed repair uptake rate and fails to account for consumer behaviors. In the real world, preferences and norms evolve and may even be influenced by the very existence of RTR legislation, where knowledge of smartphone repairability standards may increase adoption rates and psychological beliefs on longevity (Marikyan and Papagiannidis). The model assumes the consumer population as homogeneous, rather than differentiating based on demographic factors, age, income level, and pre-existing environmental awareness (Lefebvre, Lofthouse, and Wilson). Ideally, data and parameter inputs into the model can attempt to adjust for these behaviors, but predicting consumer behaviors, especially prior to the implementation of a law in the first place, may require further research into the implementation of the model. However, this data would cause the model's results to be dependent on speculative data related to parameters such as existing device longevity and adoption rates. This decreases the accuracy of the results of this model, relying on static data in a constantly changing consumer market.

Second, the model operates in isolation from market forces and excludes economic feedback loops. It does not incorporate the dynamic pricing strategies of manufacturers or the broader market effects that could alter a consumer's cost calculation when deciding between repair and replacement (Jin, Yang, and Zhu 2022). As discussed, these economic responses can have a profound, and potentially counter-intuitive, impact on the ultimate effectiveness of RTR legislation.

These limitations point toward several key areas for future research. Researchers could develop agent-based models that simulate individual decisions of consumers and manufacturer

responses, allowing the model to account for more individual behaviors and psychology. Integrating principles from behavioral economics, like perceived obsolescence and mental depreciation, could yield models that more accurately predict the adoption gap. Additionally, future Markov chain implementations could expand to include multiple failure states. Once the EU's 2030 legislation takes full effect, empirical post-hoc analysis will be crucial. Researchers must collect real-world data on repair rates, device lifespans, and market prices to better understand how to refine and improve the models developed today.

Conclusion

Through the use of a Markovian stochastic model, this research quantifies the impact of Right to Repair legislation on the average lifespan of consumer electronics, specifically through a case study of the EU's mandate for user-replaceable smartphone batteries. The case study demonstrates a potential longevity gain of 6.4% to 23.2%, a reduction in e-waste generation of 1200 metric tons and the associated manufacturing-related carbon emissions reduction of 559,350 tons by conservative estimates. However, such data relies on a level of speculative data and fails to account for consumer behavior, an avenue for future research. This finding provides quantified, evidence-based support for policies aimed at fostering a more sustainable electronics industry.

The contribution of this paper is a scalable, adaptable, and quantitative framework for evaluating the impact of specific repairability laws. It allows researchers to isolate a single design variable and better understand a single proposal through a data-driven analysis of costs and benefits. However, the analysis also reveals that the ultimate success of legislation hinges on adoption rates, a figure determined by a combination of behavioral and psychological factors that extend far beyond laws targeted at technical feasibility of repairs.

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